

compound, however, had a relaxation effect on G. I. T. The depressor effect of the compound could be of some central action.

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Synthesis of 2,3,8,9-tetrasubstituted diimidazo [2',3'-b : 2'',3''-b''] benzo [1,2-d : 4,5-d'] bithiazolo-5,11-diones—Possible Pesticides

R. P. SONI and J. P. SAXENA

Department of Chemistry, University of Jodhpur, Jodhpur-342 001

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HETEROCYCLES containing thiazole and imidazole rings have been successfully screened as anti-protozoal agents¹, anticonvulsants² and anti-diabetics³. The title compounds incorporate

has been well stressed^{4, 5} in many pesticides. Keeping the above in view, the title compounds have been synthesised with the hope that they might be pesticides of choice.

We have previously described the synthesis of thiadiazolobenzimidazoles⁶, thiazolinediones⁷, imidazolinediones⁸. The present paper deals with the synthesis of some new diimidazo-dithiazolo diones by condensing chloranil with cyclic thioureas. The products isolated were 2,3,8,9-tetrasubstituted diimidazo [2',3'-b : 2'',3''-b''] benzo [1,2-d : 4,5-d'] bithiazolo-5, 11-diones (I). All compounds of this

series gave characteristic red colour with conc. H₂SO₄.

The infrared spectra of compounds (I) showed characteristic bands at 1680-1690 (C=O), 1610-1620 (C=N) and 1065-1075, 665-675 cm⁻¹ (C-S) respectively⁹. The uv spectra of each compound showed three bands with large extinction values. Absorption at longer wavelengths in these compounds can be ascribed to the fact that there is a larger scope for electronic excitation due to resonance. The presence of group R, R₁ does not produce significant bathochromic shift.

(I)

Experimental

All melting points were determined on a Kofler Instrument and are uncorrected. IR spectra were determined on a Perkin-Elmer 677 Spectrophotometer in KBr. UV absorption spectra were recorded on a Beckman spectrophotometer Model DU-2 using 1 cm path length quartz cells.

Cyclic thioureas : The compounds were prepared by known methods^{10,11}.

2,3,8,9-tetrasubstituted diimidazo [2',3'-b : 2'',3''-b''] benzo [1,2-d : 4,5-d'] bithiazolo-5,11-diones (I) : A mixture of chloranil (0.1 mole) and cyclic thiourea (0.2 mole) in 25 ml ethanol was heated under reflux for 4 hrs. The reaction mixture was cooled basified with ammonia and again refluxed for 5 minutes. The solid separated on cooling was filtered dried and recrystallised twice from aq. ethanol. The purity of the products was established by tlc. The analysis, m.p., ir data etc. are given in Table 1.

Herbicidal screening :

Herbicidal activity was evaluated by pre-emergence tests at three concentrations viz., 1000, 100 and 10 ppm against *Argemone mexicana* and *Cyperus rotundus*. The number of replications in each case was three. Seeds/tubers of the test plants were

TABLE 1—2,3,8,9-TETRASUBSTITUTED-DIIMIDAZO[2',3'-b : 2'',3''-b'']BENZO[1,2-d : 4,5-d']BISTHIAZOLO-5,11-DIONES

Sl. No.	R	R ₁	Molecular formula	Yield %	m.p. °C	% Analysis		UV data		IR data	
						Calcd.	Found	Ethanol			
								λ _{max} nm	log ε		
1.	H	H	C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂	37	331 (decomp)	C, 47.3	46.8	281	4.56	C=O 1685, C=N 1620	
						H, 2.6	2.2	305	4.30	C-S 1970, 665 cm ⁻¹	
						N, 18.4	18.1	455	4.12		
2.	CH ₃	CH ₃	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂	43	338	C, 55.4	55.0	273	4.41	C=O 1660, C=N 1615	
						H, 3.4	3.1	314	4.27	C-S 1065, 670 cm ⁻¹	
						N, 16.1	15.7	456	4.15		
3.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂	45	285	C, 70.3	69.8	277	4.32	C=O 1690, C=N 1610	
						H, 3.2	2.8	309	4.18	C-S 1075, 675 cm ⁻¹	
						N, 9.1	8.7	447	3.97		

soaked for 24 hrs in the test solutions and planted. 2,4-D (sodium salt) was also tested under similar conditions for comparison. The percentage inhibition is recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2—HERBICIDAL SCREENING

Compound No.	Average percentage Inhibition					
	Weed <i>A. mexicana</i> concentrations used			Weed <i>C. rotundis</i> concentrations used		
	1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm	1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm
1.	60.1	32.1	24.2	53.4	20.7	13.4
2.	61.5	33.4	25.6	54.7	25.4	18.9
3.	55.1	25.4	16.5	51.3	22.7	16.4
2,4-D (Sodium salt)	100	84.2	66.7	100	82.6	61.5

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{G_c - G_t}{G_c} \times 100$$

where, G_c = No. of germinated seeds/tubers in control,

G_t = No. of germinated seeds/tubers in test solution/suspension.

Fungicidal screening :

Antifungal activity was evaluated by agar-plate technique^{1,2} against *A. niger* and *H. oryzae* at 1000, 100 and 10 ppm. The number of replication in each case was three. A commercial fungicide Dithane M-45 was tested under similar conditions for comparison. The percentage inhibition is recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 3—FUNGICIDAL SCREENING

Compound No.	Average percentage inhibition after 96 hrs					
	Organism <i>A. niger</i> concentrations used			Organism <i>H. oryzae</i> concentrations used		
	1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm	1000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm
1.	52.5	27.3	18.1	47.5	18.3	9.4
2.	57.5	30.1	21.4	57.6	22.4	13.4
3.	55.7	28.5	20.5	51.7	21.1	11.8
Dithane M-45 (a commercial fungicide)	100	85.4	72.6	96.4	82.9	68.3

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{(C - T) \times 100}{C}$$

where, C = Diameter of fungus colony in control plates after 96 hrs,

T = Diameter of fungus colony in treated plates after 96 hrs.

It is evident from the screening data (Tables 2 and 3) that all the screened compounds were toxic to weeds (*A. mexicana* and *C. rotundus*) and fungi (*A. niger* and *H. Oryzae*) in varied degrees. Compound No. 2 in both the cases inhibited 50% growth of both the fungi and weed at 1000 ppm and thus appear to be fairly active.

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Synthesis and Fungitoxicity of Some Bicyclic Compounds

P. MITTRA and A. S. MITTRA*

Mayurbhanj Chemical Laboratory, Ravenshaw College, Cuttack-753 003

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5-Mono-bromo-3-N-phenyl-rhodanine¹ when condensed with acetoacetic ester in presence of ethanol affords 3-N-phenyl-5-(1'-acetyl-1'-carboethoxy methyl)-rhodanine, which on condensation with phenyl hydrazine yields 3-N-phenyl-5-(1'-phenyl - 3'-methyl - 2'-pyrazolin-5'-ones)-rhodanine. This compound also synthesized by two other methods in which 5-mono-bromo-3-phenyl-rhodanine condensed in ethanol with 1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one and 4-mono-bromo-1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one in presence of ethanol with 3-N-phenyl-rhodanine afford the same compound. The product obtained by the three methods were found identical from their m. m. p. and superimposition of ir data. The oxidation of the above compound resulting in the conversion of $\text{>C}-\text{C}<$ to $\text{>C}=\text{C}<$ was accomplished by the treatment of the alkaline solution of 3-phenyl-5-(1'-phenyl - 3'-methyl-2'-pyrazolin-5'-one)-rhodanine with saturated solution of iodine in potassium iodide.

In our previous work²⁻⁵ on heterocyclic five membered compounds, we reported the significant

* Address for correspondence, C/o, K. C. Mittra, Rashbehari Math Lane, Taltelanga Bazar, Cuttack-753 009.